

TECHNIQUES OF FOREGROUNDING IN THE ANALYSIS OF THE TEXT

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Annotation:

Foregrounding is defined as a literary device that emphasizes ideas and characters by leading from attention-grabbing linguistic techniques that repeat content or disrupt specific patterns. Foregrounding is a literary device that emphasizes ideas and symbols through attention-seeking techniques.

Key words: Foregrounding, derivatives, parallelism: (anaphora; antithesis; asyndeton and epistrophe techniques) and deviation, symbol, linguistics, cognitive linguistics.

INTRODUCTION

Foregrounding is used to draw the reader's attention to specific points or details in the text. Linguistic features or parts of the text are the first to match. This happens when something in the text is foreshadowed. Pointing forward is synonymous with center, focal point, and focus.

Foregrounding refers to an image, symbol, or language that is significant or important. A device for demiliarizing or alienating the reader from the text and content. Derivatives in form and language provide new perspectives and responses to texts. Produced by Viktor Shkolvsky (1893-1984) and later by Jan Mukarovsky (1891-1975). Foregrounding makes an image, symbol, or language a prominent or important feature. Although the device is produced for literary-aesthetic purposes, it is also common to place the foreground in order to expand the perspectives in the

picture.

METHODOLOGY

Foregrounding is used to estrange or defamiliarise the reader so they gain new perspectives on the text. The act of foregrounding in literature serves to raise the reader's attention to the text. The reader will learn more about the meaning of the picture and the author's choice. Consider what word or pattern (broken or repeated) the author wants to draw the reader's attention to experience epiphanies or a work of art or literature for a new one.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Foregrounding in linguistic text gains meaning **as a contrast to the background**. The figure seen against the background is applied to poetry, where the [narrator](#) or the subject of the poem is measured against the background of a regular or expected pattern.

In Dylan Thomas's elegy 'A Grief Ago' (1935), the figure of grief is 'She', the 'rose maid' or 'masted venus' who stands foregrounded against a backdrop filled with imagery such as the tower, the sea, and the sun. The grief Thomas experiences is focused on the figure of 'She'.

A grief ago, She who was who I hold, the fats and flower, Or, water-lammed, from the scythe-sided thorn, Hell wind and sea, A stem cementing, wrestled up the tower, Rose maid and male, Or, masted venus, through the paddler's bowl Sailed up the sun.

The title of 'A grief ago' is doubly foregrounded. Grief is an emotional word rather than a marker of time (such as week or day), and so appears grammatically incorrect. The grammatical inconsistency makes the word stand out. Dylan Measuring time through emotions was asked to think by Thomas. Foregrounding,

however, is not as simple as contrasting a figure with its background. Specific words in literature are also used to show contrast and estrangement.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Foregrounding methods include any stylistic violations, "through the side of the text that deviates from the language norm, or alternatively, one side of the text is brought to the fore through repetition or parallelism" (Azam Esmaili. , 2013). Parallelism and deviation are used to draw attention to the strangeness of a word or the actions of a character in a literary work. Previewing is achieved through these techniques.

Figure 1. Methods of foregrounding

Parallelism repeats content with surprising regularity. It is the repetition of sounds, meanings, structures, and grammatical elements in written and spoken language to emphasize relationships between aspects of a text. Sometimes

parallelism occurs in single words with little change in meaning, such as "bend" and "curve" or "ascent" and "ascent" for thematic emphasis. Other times it is a literary device that creates parallel positions between opposing ideas. Parallelism can be reversed to increase emphasis in sentences and plots.

Table 2

Examples of parallelism in literature text

№	Text	Samples
1	Alexander Pope's <i>The Rape of the Lock</i> (1714) features parallelism through alliteration.	Resolved to win, he meditates the way, By force to ravish, or by fraud betray.
2	AR Ammons's <i>Small Song</i> (1990) shows parallelism in enjambment and the play of 'give way' with 'give away'.	The reeds give way to the Wind and give the wind away
3	James Baldwin's speech 'As Much Truth as One Can Bear' in 1962.	Not everything that is faced can be changed; but nothing can be changed until it is faced.

Parallelism repeats content with unexpected regularity to emphasize relations. Parallelism is considered under the category of figures of speech. The technique takes forms such as:(see figure 1)

Figure 2. Techniques of parallelism

The effect of the repeated phrase in poetry and novels emphasizes the development of the work's content through identical phrases and subtle or overt changes to that phrase. Thus, the text is foregrounded by the repeated patterns, and these emphasize the modifications of the repeated phrases. This should not be forgotten that parallelism and repetition differ because parallelism repeats content but with slight modifications, while repetition is the reuse of words, phrases and themes.

Deviation is an unexpected irregularity that enhances the reader's sense of dislocation from the literary work. Deviation is the setting up, and the deliberate breaking of, established patterns of language or sound. In poetry, deviations frequently occur in [rhythm](#), rhyme, stanza [layout](#), and any images or symbols

which look out of place. Deviation is characterized as an unexpected irregularity of words, metaphors, and character development which work to enhance the reader's sense of dislocation from the literary work. In addition, deviation violates rules and conventions.

Table 3**Examples of deviation in literature text**

№	Text	Samples
1	John Hopkins's 'The Wreck of the Deutschland' (1918) features deviation in its choice of words. Here, a form of deviation called lexical deviation occurs in Stanza 13:	<p><i>Wiry and white-fiery and whirlwind-swivellèd snow</i></p> <p><i>Spins to the widow-making unchilding unfathering deeps.</i></p>
<p><i>Hopkins uses the prefix 'un' to create new words not normally used in Standard English. Such a rule break is further emphasized by the previous line's multiple uses of internal rhyme ('wi-ry' and 'fie-ry') and the alliteration of 'w'. The 'w' sounds different from the 'u' which shows the unsettling deviation visually and sonically. Thus, the unchilding and unfathering has a more dramatic impact in the stanza. The word is placed in the foreground to emphasize its significance in the poem.</i></p>		

There are several types of deviation (see table 3):

Table 4

Types of deviation

№	types of deviation	Definition
	Grammatical	either morphological or syntactic (ie. Bad grammar or syntax rearrangement).
	Lexical	playing with word meanings and definitions to create new words (such as Hopkin's unchilding and TS Eliot's foresuffered in 'The Wasteland' (1922)).
	Phonological	how language and sounds are affected by omissions or dialect spellings.
	Semantic	the play of meaning, with a frequent exploration of absurdity and nonsense (such as William Wordsworth's 'The child is father of the man' in 'My Heart Leaps Up' (1807)).
	Textual	how text is affected by the deviation
	Graphological	visual patterning of words, punctuation, or the poem itself
	Dialectal	the borrowing of features of regional or social dialects / slang (think of Alice Walker's The Color Purple (1982) and the use of African American Vernacular English, or Ebonics). This, too, relies on linguistics.
	Register	is a 'language variety used by a particular group of people who share the same occupation.' Register mixing as a register deviation.

	Historical period	genre mixing or using archaic expressions of words in modern contexts, or vice versa.
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Deviation is distinguished by the reader's response to certain language use and linguistic structure. External and internal deviations **are deviations from some norm which is internal or external** to the text. External and internal deviations are best seen in poetry. Any word, phrase, or sound that deviates from the norm is foregrounding. They are deviations from some norm that is internal or external to the text.

Table 5

According to the language use and linguistic structure, deviation types

Types	Definition	Samples
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External deviation	External deviation is when the author or poet breaks from the normal conventions of language use - such as sentences that are not grammatically correct or the use of nonsense words.	The Dylan Thomas example of 'A Grief Ago' is an example of an external deviation because the poet's choice of 'grief' in the title deviates from normal poetic word and grammar choices.
		George Herbert's poem 'Easter Wings' (1633) is another external deviation because the structure of the poem is meant to mimic angel wings while revisiting the ancient Greek tradition of shaped poems. The poem's structure is placed in the foreground to emphasise its significance in the poem. Herbert's poem Easter Wings uses external deviation as the text is arranged to look like angel wings.
Internal deviation	Internal deviation is when the author or poet breaks from a pattern they have previously set up in the text, usually to striking effect	(as an example of foregrounding).

Foregrounding is used to estrange or defamiliarise the reader so they gain new perspectives on the text.

CONCLUSION

In general, foregrounding is a literary device that emphasizes ideas and symbols through attention-seeking techniques. Foregrounding refers to an image, symbol, or language that is significant or important. Foregrounding methods include any stylistic violations; parallelism and deviation are used to draw attention to the strangeness of a word or the actions of a character in a literary work. Previewing is achieved through these techniques. Parallelism repeats content with unexpected regularity to emphasize relations. It includes anaphora; antithesis; asyndeton and epistrophe techniques. Deviation is an unexpected irregularity that enhances the reader's sense of dislocation from the literary work. It is divided subtypes that External and internal deviations are deviations from some norm which is internal or external to the text.

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